

**МЕВА ВА САБЗАВОТ МАҲСУЛОТЛАРНИ САҚЛАШ
ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ**

Khalikov Muhridin Mardikulovich - basic doctoral student of the Navoi State
Pedagogical Institute

Djuraev Khairullo Fayziyevich - professor, Bukhara Institute of Engineering
Technology

Nasirova Shaira Narmuradovna - professor, Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract

This article covers the information about the technology of storage of fruit and vegetable products. In the sustainable development of fruit and vegetable production, the use of advanced technologies of product cultivation, the introduction of modern methods of product processing and storage make it possible to prevent food shortages today.

Key words: fruit, vegetable, product, storage, technology, natural, method, artificial, substance.

Globally, the demand for seasonal fruits and vegetables rich in natural vitamins, micro- and macroelements is increasing year by year. At the same time, the reforms carried out on improving the technology of freezing, improving the productivity of fruits, which determine their unique taste along with natural mono- and disaccharides, keep their organic acids within standards, are of urgent importance.

In the global food industry, scientific research is being conducted on the preservation of fruits and vegetables based on high-quality and energy-efficient technologies. In this regard, special attention is paid to the development and testing of technologies for preserving fruits rich in vitamins and minerals, which preserve the values of the main color parameters, textural parameters and enzymatic activity during the periods of traditional and shock freezing.

In recent years, certain results have been achieved in our republic on the modernization of food industry enterprises, expansion of the types and size of

<http://innconferences.iblogger.org/>

competitive products, development of promising and effective freezing technologies for preserving cherry fruits, which are considered important sources of biologically active substances grown in Uzbekistan. In the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan, the important tasks of "deepening the structural changes and consistent development of the processing capacity of agricultural products, further strengthening the country's food security, expanding the production of ecologically clean, high-quality products, significantly increasing the export potential of the agricultural sector" given [1]

In the sustainable development of fruit and vegetable production, the use of advanced technologies of product cultivation, the introduction of modern methods of product processing and storage make it possible to prevent food shortages today. It is known that grown fruits and vegetables go through a number of technological processes before reaching the consumer in the form of a finished product.

It is known that the people of our republic have great experience and a long history in storing fruits and vegetables. Today, there are the following methods of storing fruits and vegetables:

- natural storage: the products are stored in different cellars and warehouses, it is not possible to control the storage process, that is, in this case, the products depend on the temperature and humidity of the environment;

- artificial storage: in artificial storage of agricultural products, products are stored in specially designed buildings.

Today, more than 80% of preserved and consumed products on the world market are artificially preserved products. With the help of special equipment, in the cooling chambers in the buildings, an environment is created and kept, which ensures the condition of fruits and vegetables in a freshly cut state.

The main purpose of storing agricultural products is to preserve and deliver to the consumer all the substances useful for the human body, collected by the raw

<http://innconferences.iblogger.org/>

materials before ripening. During the storage of fruits and vegetables, several main reasons for the loss of useful nutrients can be indicated, which are as follows:

- decrease in the quality of raw materials and loss of substances:
- • factors related to conditions of cultivation and agrotechnical processing, violation of harvesting methods and conditions, changes in their composition under the influence of various diseases (microorganisms, parasites), gnawing of raw materials by various creatures;

decrease in the quality of fruits and vegetables as a result of respiration and loss of moisture.

Today, with the development of science and technology, a number of modern technologies for maximum preservation of the quality of fruits and vegetables have been created and put into practice.

The main ones of these styles are:

- lowering the temperature of the storage chamber;
- optimization of relative humidity in the cooling chamber;
- change the air content in the cooling chamber.

After fruits and vegetables are harvested, the opposite of this process begins, that is, as a result of their absorption of oxygen in the air, carbon dioxide gas, moisture and a certain amount of heat are released. Such processes in fruits and vegetables are called metabolism or aging process.

The main goal of agricultural storage and processing specialists is to preserve useful substances in raw materials by preventing the metabolic processes mentioned above. This requires a great deal of knowledge from specialists. After all, for each fruit or vegetable placed in storage warehouses, it is necessary to approach them based on their chemical composition. Today, science and technology are developing and many achievements are being made, that is, as a result of creating conditions during the storage process of products, it is possible to preserve their contents in the same state as when they were freshly cut.

REFERENCES:

1. 1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 PF-60 "On the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026".
2. Xoliqov M.M., Nasirova Sh.N. Fruit drying methods and their useful features. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal 2023, Volume 1 Issue 9, Rossiya, 157-162 pp
3. Kholikov M.M., Djuraev Kh.F., Nasirova Sh.N. The importance of improving the drying processes of fruit and vegetable pastilles. UNIVERSUM: «Технические науки» № 7 (100), М., Изд. «МЦНО», 2022, Россия, 34-38 p.